

ISSUES OF CARTOGRAPHIC SUPPLY OF THE UNIFIED STATE CADASTRES SYSTEM

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Abstract. In the article, in order to collect state cadastre information and form their database, it is effective in maintaining state cadastres, methods of geodetic and cartographic provision of the cadastral field based on modern geographic information systems, as well as registering cadastral objects, designing and compiling their digital maps. ways of using technologies are described. Also, information on the main characteristics, scale, legend and conditional signs of cadastral cards is provided, in accordance with the requirements of the state cadastral service and the structure of the cards taking into account the capabilities of the users.

Key words. GAT, AKT, legend, generalization, map creation principles, geographical coordinates, methodology, cartographic model, analytical map, inventory map, digital map, cadastral map.

Enter. In the conditions of the rapid growth and development of the telecommunications sector in the world, their management in accordance with modern technologies and rapid monitoring are of particular importance. In this regard, it is necessary to carry out targeted scientific research aimed at the development of effective technologies for the registration of cadastral objects, the design and creation of digital maps of cadastral objects on the basis of modern

geographic information systems. attention is being paid. In this regard, one of the important tasks is to improve the method of creating and updating cadastral cards of communication objects, to develop modern technologies for updating digital cards.

Currently, cadastral works in our republic and their geodesic, cartographic provision, implementation of complex measures for updating cadastral cards, including cadastre of communication objects, construction of new telecommunications facilities, use of modern computer technologies in the development of their projects to improve the infrastructure of existing ones, Comprehensive measures are being implemented on the location of the cadastral objects, which are the main indicators of the state cadastral objects, based on their address and geographical coordinates.

In the decision PQ-3662 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated April 11, 2018 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the public service delivery system", the state and economy in our republic said that it is necessary to implement a number of measures in order to increase the efficiency of the activities of administrative bodies, local government bodies, to ensure the wide use of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) in the field of state and community building [3].

K.A. Salishev, I.P.Zaruskaya, A.P.Zolovsky, P.P.Lebedev, I.Yu.Levisky, V.P.Razov and others contributed a lot to the theoretical and practical foundations of the problems of designing and compiling cadastral maps. The following scientists contributed to the formation of cadastral cartography in Uzbekistan: A. Abduazizov, S.A. Avezbayev, R.A.Tolipov, E.Yu.Safarov, Q.Rakhmonov, T.Mirzaliyev, J.S.Koraboyev, B.T.Kurbanov, A.A.Tursunov and others.

Today, in the scientific works of the above-mentioned scientists, there are enough problems related to the cadastral indicators of communication objects, ways of collecting them, the role of GAT technologies, the principles of creating

cadastral cards, and their improvement and development in the era of new century technologies. not studied to the extent.

The main part. The development of a cartographic model, which summarizes the geographic location of objects, their mutual relations, structure, quality and quantity indicators, as well as their price, cost and legal status in accordance with conventional symbols, is the scientific and theoretical basis for creating cadastral cards and plans. . Map and place models allow to describe information and data collected about events and events in unique ways.

Cadastral cards have the following features:

- the geometrical similarity of the objects when represented on the map and plan ensures that their shape and size are very close to real life, and the level of accuracy in the plans is even higher. This feature of cards ensures that cartographic works are accurately carried out on the map within the given scale;
- represents changes over time. Cards show the state and development of events and events in a certain period (time, century, year, month, day, etc.);
- the similarity of relations and internal relations of mutual events and events with each other;
- compatibility of objects with each other; One of the main characteristics of cadastral maps and plans is that the events and incidents depicted on the map match each other according to the situation on the ground and do not negate each other. Content compatibility also depends on the overlap of borders, the study of mutual relations and hierarchy of events and phenomena on cadastral maps, the accuracy and scientific basis of data, the application of the process of generalization when depicted on maps and plans. [56];
- exact correspondence of models and objects to each other is one of the characteristics of state cadastral plans and cards (especially since they are analytical and inventory cards), etc.

The level of abstraction in cadastral plans and maps depends on the level of

generalization and generalization of events and incidents described in them. Selection, summarization and processing of information in accordance with the purpose allows to direct the content of the card to one goal.

As an object of state cadastral plans and cards, 20 state cadastral objects operating within the framework of the unified state cadastral system are used to collect their natural, socio-economic resources and various assets of the national economy.

In the management of the state cadastral system, large-scale cadastral cards are one of the main documents. This is reflected in the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on state cadastres [1].

Along with all state cadastres, the state cadastre of communication objects is also subject to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Cadastres" (15.12.2000 No. 171-II) [1], the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Postal Communication "(31.08.2000 No. 118-II) [2], the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Telecommunications" (08.20.1999 No. 822-I) [4] and Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan According to the Regulation "On the procedure for creating and maintaining a unified system of state cadastres" approved by the decision No. 66 of February 16, 2005, and "The procedure for maintaining the state cadastre of communication objects" on June 30, 2005 No. 152 on approval of the Regulation" [4].

The design and creation of cadastral plans and maps is a complex process, because according to the purpose and tasks of the map, the qualitative and quantitative indicators of the events and phenomena described in them are determined, analyzed, evaluated, and linked to a certain geographical area in the map and plan. finds the opposite.

The system of cadastral cards includes information about the current state of social, economic and natural resources distributed in a certain natural or administrative area. Development of the content of cadastral cards in accordance

with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on state cadastres adopted on December 15, 2000, the geographical location, status, quantity, quality indicators of a certain type of natural, social and economic or other wealth maintained by the state cadastre and is a system of updated information and documents about the price [1].

A cadastral card or plan is a graphic image and drawings reflecting the location and boundaries of objects subject to cadastral works, their assessment, quantity and quality indicators, and it is created on paper and other means.

The structure of the unified system of state cadastres of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of 20 types. The content of cadastral cards of each of them is developed separately.

Land cadastre cards are cards that reflect the geographic location, types, categories, size, credit score, use and land ownership status of objects on the ground. Land cadastral cards are drawn up for all land used in the national economy and land intended for agriculture (irrigated, semi-arid, perennial gardens, gray lands, pastures and other rural, farm lands).

Land maps for settlements, industry, transport, communication, defense, nature protection, recreation, forest fund, water fund, reserve, historical and other purposes are drawn up separately depending on the needs of the cadastral system.

The state forest cadastre maps show the geographical distribution areas of forests, their types, tree height, density, age and amount of wood. A separate ypg'y is given to which category the forests are suitable for. (Industry, protection, environment, etc.). Artificially and naturally regenerated forests, their types, quality and quantity indicators are correctly evaluated and described.

Separately protected natural areas are state cadastral cards, these are reserves, orders (zakaznik), maps of natural landmarks. This map describes the geographical location and boundaries of the protected area, as well as the qualitative and quantitative indicators of the natural and economic resources

found there.

The location, floor and rooms of the building are described in the state cadastral cards of buildings and structures. The type, price and cost of construction materials used for each building are shown. The types of equipment used for the building (elevator, pump, etc.) are also explained. Telephone networks, sewage pipes and in which area (zone) of the city are located are indicated.

Cards of the state cadastre of historical and cultural monuments contain detailed information on the geographical location of the monuments, the time of their construction, their type, and their current condition. A separate cadastral plan is prepared for each monument with quality and quantity indicators, reflecting the type and method of use.

Road and railway state cadastre cards contain quality and quantity indicators of roads, i.e. highways, width, length, service area, type of road surface and their cost. reflect. The cadastral card of railways shows the number of tracks of the railway, the time it was built and put into operation, electrification, and the amount of passenger and cargo transportation.

The state cadastre cards of transport pipelines describe the year of construction, type, time of commissioning of pipelines, type of products transported in them, quality and quantity indicators. Warehouses where products are stored, their equipment, types of equipment and cost are shown. The direction, depth and geographical location of the pipelines are clearly expressed.

The state cadastral cards of communication facilities reflect the geographical location, status, type of service, amount and prices of communication facilities. Amplification stations and the width of their sphere of influence are given in kilometers, and the coordinates of their location are clearly indicated.

Cartography-geodesy state cadastral cards indicate the availability of

cartographic data of the Republic of Uzbekistan, their type, scale, quantity and year of publication. For each piece of information, the territory occupied and its modernity are clearly indicated.

The unified system of state cadastres may include other state cadastres determined by law. It is natural that the content and scale of cadastral maps and plans change and improve according to the needs of the times, because these maps and plans are constantly and regularly updated, they must reflect the changes in nature and production.

It requires the use of cartographic research methods to study, analyze and evaluate changing socio-economic and natural phenomena, their regional differentiation, qualitative and quantitative indicators. These methods make it possible to determine not only regional differentiation, but also the system of regional natural and economic complexes corresponding to them, the laws of their development, and create an opportunity to create various scientifically based predictions and measures.

Selection of scale of cadastral cards. State cadastral cards can be created and printed for different purposes and in different directions. The scale of the maps depends on the requirements for their accuracy, the issues to be solved and the work to be carried out [5].

It depends on the purpose of state cadastral cards, user demand and carrying out cartometric measurements. Cards can be complex (complex) or branched (field) according to this requirement. The scale for plans and cards is selected according to the requirements of enterprises and institutions that use cadastral plans, cards and information (household services, taxation, urban planning, automobile and railway services, agriculture, energy, etc.). The content of the cadastral cards, aimed at one goal, contains information and indicators about the cadastral system of one or another type of natural and socio-economic resources (soil, water, buildings, minerals, etc.) reflects [6].

The objectivity, correctness and modernity of cadastral plans and maps, a clear geographical basis for their creation, new data obtained with modern equipment, surveys, practical field work, aerospace photographs and computers were achieved. Cadastral plans and cards created on the basis of such detailed documents and information are mainly used for practical work. Therefore, it is advisable to use a series of scales ranging from 1:100 to 1:2000 for this type of card. However, the general planning of the national economy is carried out on the scale of a district, region or republic. The cadastral cards intended for these works require the generalization (generalization) of many indicators and information in some natural or political administrative areas. It is advisable to prepare cadastral cards on a scale of 1:100,000 to 1:1,000,000 for running and managing the cadastral system.

Based on the basic principles (principles) of state cadastre management, the following scales are recommended for the composition of the unified system of state cadastres:

1. For state land cadastre cards, mainly from 1:1,000 to 1:200,000, depending on their scope and purpose. It will be necessary to prepare plans and maps on a scale of 1:1,000 for irrigated lands, 1:5,000 for rainfed lands, 1:100,000 for mountain pastures, and 1:200,000 for plain pastures.

2. The scale of 1:100 to 1:100,000 is recommended for state cadastral maps of mineral deposits, signs and man-made formations. Scales of 1:1 00 - 1:10 000 are appropriate for man-made formations and open pit mines.

3. For the state water cadastre, the use of scales of 1:50,000 and 1:200,000 is effective.

4. 1:10,000 to 1:200,000 scale for the state forest cadastre, 1:50,000 to 1:200,000 scale for the state cadastre of flora and fauna.

5. Scales from 1:200,000 to 1:500,000 are recommended for the state cadastre of the animal world, because these maps mainly show the habitats of the

animal species.

6. It is recommended to use scales of 1:1000-1:10,000 for state cadastre of specially protected natural areas and state cadastre of borders with high natural risk and state cadastre of areas with high man-made risk. The scale of 1:1000-1:10,000 is recommended for state cadastral maps of industrial and consumer waste disposal sites.

7. 1:100, 1:500, 1:1000, 1:2000 and 1:5000 and 1:10000 scales should be used for the state cadastre of buildings and structures and the state urban development cadastre.

8. State cadastre of hydraulic facilities; 1:100, 1:500, 1:1000 and 1:2000 scales are required for the state cadastre of communication objects and the state cadastre of energy objects.

9. Scales of 1:10000, 1:100000 -1:500000 are recommended for plans and maps of the state cadastre of automobile roads, state cadastre of railways and state cadastre of transport pipelines.

10. 1:100 and 1:200,000 scales for the state cadastre of historical and cultural monuments. 1:100-1000 scale plans for monuments, 1:200,000 scale maps of their distribution over certain areas can be made.

11. It is appropriate to use scales of 1:100,000 - 1:500,000 when compiling the state cadastre of cartography and geodesy.

12. State cadastral maps of communication facilities should be drawn up in urban areas on a scale of 1:1000-1:2000, and in rural areas on a scale of 1:10,000-25,000.

The legend and conditional symbols of state cadastral cards must be made in accordance with the requirements of the state cadastral service and taking into account the capabilities of card users.

Therefore, the quality, accuracy, modernity and reliability of the content of any card will always depend on the quality of the resources involved in creating

this card.

Currently, the global positioning system (GPS) is used to create geodetic networks. This system is based on the use of earth's satellites to determine the coordinates of the desired point on the earth's surface. This is the main method for creating the geodetic basis of cadastral maps and plans.

Summary. As a result of the conducted research, state registration of state cadastral objects, collection of cadastral data and the formation and maintenance of their database, methods of geodetic and cartographic provision of the cadastral field on the basis of modern geographic information systems and cadastral objects. The ways of using effective technologies in registration, design and creation of their digital cards, as well as the main features, scale, legend and conventional signs of cadastral cards are justified in accordance with the requirements of the state cadastral service and taking into account the capabilities of card users.

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